

**MOORING DESIGN AND ANALYSIS METHODS
WITHIN THE NAVAL FACILITIES ENGINEERING COMMAND**

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ABSTRACT

A family of design and analysis methods for mooring ships and other platforms over a wide range of environmental conditions are summarized. These methods address "Fleet" or "free" moorings, not pier moorings. The Naval Facilities Engineering Command designs standard fleet, specialized deep water, and storm moorings for naval vessels, and moorings for other platforms such as dry docks and barges. Design and analysis methods range from a design manual to computer aided design. The methods are described and compared. The appropriate use of each is described along with example applications.

INTRODUCTION

"Fleet" or "free" Moorings are tension member structures used to moor vessels of the U.S. Navy, including active surface ships, submarines, services vessels (such as barges and floating dry docks), and inactive ships. Figure 1 illustrates a typical single-point Fleet Mooring. Moorings are used in a "freeswing" or single-point mode, in two-point bow-stern configurations, or to hold a ship from multiple points as illustrated in Figure 2. Fleet Moorings can be categorized according to use as:

Standard operational moorings - used for active ships that can exit during extreme conditions such as an approaching storm;

Storm moorings - used in cases where ships cannot exit during severe weather such as inactive ships or barges; and

Specialized moorings - used for floating drydocks or other unusual applications such as taut moorings to restrict the moored vessels motion.

The number and sophistication of required analyses increase going from standard to specialized or more complex mooring requirements.

DESIGN METHODS

A majority of design is based on the "quasi-static" approach. In this approach, statistical methods are used to define the environmental and design parameters. Next, forces and moments on the ship due to the design wind, current and wave drift are treated as

static (statistical methods and factors of safety effectively convert real world conditions into events used in "quasi-static" design parameters). Finally, moorings are designed to resist forces and moments and satisfy other design criteria, such as watch circle, limited capacity of ship's hardware, etc. In some cases the tentative designs are then tested and refined using dynamic analyses.

Three fairly complete design methodologies, along with four specialized analysis tools, are described here and are available for the designer to select from. The designer must determine the types of analyses required, then select the proper design methodology(s) and any additional special analysis tools necessary to perform each of these required analyses. For more complex problems, the designer will often have to use the simpler methods first in order to get a preliminary design and to determine which of the more sophisticated methodologies is appropriate for the final design. Table I lists the methodologies and analysis tools discussed here and several of their key characteristics.

TABLE I. DESIGN METHODS/TOOLS AND THEIR CHARACTERISTICS

Methodology/Tool	Computer	Application
DM 26.5	None (manual)	Complete design - Quasi-static
LOAD Program	Microcomputer	Tool, force determination - Quasi-static
EI Program	Mini/microcomputer	Tool, Mooring leg analysis - Quasi-static, 3-D legs
FLSET Program	Microcomputer	Tool, Ship position determination - Quasi-static, 2-D legs
1-D Resonance	Microcomputer	Tool, Ship motion - dynamic, time domain, 1-D analysis
FLSETHOR	Large Micro	Complete design - Quasi-static, 2-D legs, interactive design and graphics
SEADYN-86	Mainframe	Complete design - Dynamic, frequency domain, full 3-D with forces on all mooring components
SEADYN-87	Minicomputer	Same as 86 version but with interactive design and graphics (1987 release)

DESIGN MANUAL

The simpler, single or two-point mooring in relatively protected waters, such as those in the first category described above, can often be designed utilizing the NAVFAC Fleet Mooring Design Manual - DM-26.5, reference 1. In this design manual approach the emphasis is placed on standard pre-engineered designs for the following reasons:

(a) There are a large number of Navy Fleet Moorings, over 200 world-wide, thus significant design costs and time savings can be realized;

(b) They emphasize high safety and strive to reduce costs, especially maintenance costs, and standard designs can accommodate most mooring needs;

(c) Most moorings are placed in protected harbors, so wind and current forces predominate;

(d) These pre-engineered designs have been developed and have evolved based on many years of design experience using a variety of analytical models, much prototype testing, and decades of actual mooring usage; and

(e) Materials are inventoried to service the standard designs to allow both rapid installation of new moorings and maintenance of existing moorings, all at a reasonable cost.

While these standard designs have broad applications, the DM 26.5 methodology can be utilized only if the following conditions are not present:

- Waves..... > 1.5 ft for small craft
> 4.0 ft for larger vessels
- Wind..... > 60 knots
- Hurricanes and..... All cases where the
Typhoons vessel must remain moored
- Seiche..... Possibly a problem for
taut or multiple point moorings
- Short-Scope Moorings Those subjected to wave
or surge conditions
- Current..... > 3 knots
- Water Depth..... > 150 ft
- Anchors..... Other than
drag-embedment,
dead-weight or stake
pile types
- Ice..... Any presence

If these conditions are present, more sophisticated design and analysis tools are required such as those listed in subsequent sections.

This DM-26.5 approach is quasi-static. It addresses wind velocity on a statistical worst case basis, and calculates wind and current forces on the ships actual cross-sections. Empirical factors are added to account for the effect of shallow water on current drag forces, and for minor wave loading. This methodology does consider the increased forces on the vessel caused by the typically non-aligned wind and current in sheltered water locations. This approach utilizes standard mooring classes as shown in Table II. For a given mooring class and

ship, the designer must still determine under what conditions the mooring can be used.

Table II. STANDARD U.S. NAVY MOORING CLASSES

Mooring Class	Working Capacity (kips)	Rigging Chain Size* (inches)
AA	300	4.00
BB	250	3.50
CC	200	3.50
DD	175	3.00
A	150	2.75
B	125	2.50
C	100	2.25
D	75	2.00
E	50	1.75

* Assumes Class FM3 Mooring Chain which now includes a zinc anode on each link to provide cathodic protection.

LOAD PROGRAM

This is a simple microcomputer program that automates the environmental force prediction portions (current and wind drag) of the DM-26.5 methodology. The wind and current velocity and their direction (or range of directions) are input along with the ship's cross-sectional characteristics. The program does the routine calculations and is particularly practical where a number of combinations must be examined, as in the example below. The output tables can be used in a variety of ways, including as input to the FLEET program described below.

This program can also be used to assist in the quasi-static analysis of one of the dynamic loading effects common to protected waters. Since vessels will typically yaw or "fish-tail" 20 to 30 degrees from their so-called equilibrium position, increased forces result. The program calculates the forces on the ship at 1-degree increments for reasonable angles on either side of its predicted steady-state orientation in the mooring. The peak quasi-static force can be estimated using this method (see Figure 3).

EI PROGRAM

The "EI" program was developed to analyze complex mooring leg configurations that include catenaries, chain and lines of different weights, multiple sinkers, out-of-plane components (such as multiple ground legs running off from a ground ring at different angles), equalizers and submersible buoys. Figure 4 illustrates a typically complex three-dimensional mooring leg configuration which the EI program can routinely handle. The output is an accurate load-deflection curve for the mooring leg. Figure 5 is a typical resulting load-deflection curve.

FLEET PROGRAM

FLEET, like LOAD, is a program that was developed for use in conjunction with DM-26.5. It utilizes catenary equations and an iterative procedure to determine single or multi-point mooring equilibrium configurations and resulting loads on individual mooring legs. Inputs are anchor and chock coordinates; mooring leg

load-deflection curve (from the EI Program or calculated by hand for simple configurations); lateral and longitudinal loading, and applied moments on the vessel (from LOAD, DM-26.5, or other sources); and desired convergence accuracy. In the program, the environmental loading is not varied as the vessel yaws in the mooring.

1-D RESONANCE PROGRAM

Even in protected waters a ship's surging motion, although small, can lead to significant loading of the mooring in two situations:

- (a) Where the mooring system is very taut or highly non-linear, very small displacements can lead to high loading; or
- (b) For the case where the mooring is poorly designed/matched for the vessel, the ship and mooring can get into a resonance condition where motions and forces can be amplified.

Some dynamic effects can be modelled without going through a full, time-consuming, dynamic analysis. This simplified one-dimensional time-domain analysis utilizes classical damped harmonic oscillator analysis (reference 2) to examine response to long period forcing. A non-linear load-deflection curve, such as shown in Figure 5, can be used to account for hawser stretch, submergence and rotation of the buoy, and lifting of the sinker. Forcing functions can include the reversing current component of long waves (using techniques outlined in reference 3) and/or a wind spectrum. The latter can be generated by the computer using wind energy components with periods between five seconds and one hour. This technique is based on earlier work by J. Vellozzi, et al, reference 4. Ship mass, added mass, and damping are considered in this time-marching scheme which updates the forcing, restoring, and ship conditions at one-second intervals. A typical resulting mooring line tension history is shown in Figure 6. While this technique over-simplifies the problem to a one-dimensional case, it has proven reliable in identifying problem situations and in estimating some critical dynamic effects in environments generally addressable with quasi-static techniques. This tool can also be used to estimate the effects of seiches, the use of the mooring to brake a moving vessel, or sudden release of tension from a leg.

EXAMPLE OF FLEET MOORING DESIGN

The key inputs and results of an example problem utilizing most of the above analysis tools are summarized in Table III. In this example, a storm mooring is to be designed to hold two minesweepers inside a harbor entrance during a hurricane. Site-specific environmental

data is available (see Table III) and only minor extrapolation is required for the 200-year storm design criteria. See reference 5 for more details on this example design problem.

Use of either DM-26.5 or the LOAD program gives a maximum quasi-static load in the mooring of 59 kips. The next check is for maximum loading due to the "fish-tailing" of the moored vessels in the mooring. The LOAD program was used to calculate the mooring force as a result of yaw angle relative to the equilibrium orientation (see Figure 3). For a maximum yaw angle of +/- 30 degrees, the maximum estimated load on the mooring is 80 kips.

Since peak dynamic loads are also a function of the actual mooring hardware, a mooring configuration must be selected and evaluated on a trial-and-error basis. This design process must then be iterated until a reasonable design results. Either hand calculations or the EI program can be used to develop the load-deflection curve for each mooring configuration considered. Figure 5 is the resulting curve for the final mooring configuration. This load-deflection curve, a computer generated current surge and wind gust time history, together with other inputs listed above under the description of the 1-D Resonance Program, are used to calculate a surge force time history for the most severe combination of conditions. Figure 6 illustrates this time history and indicates the maximum load to be 90 kips. Since this load is larger than the "fish-tailing" load, the 90 kip load will be used as the maximum design load for the mooring system. Thus, the hardware sized for a Class "C" Mooring, rated at a 100-kip capacity and including the factor of safety, is appropriate.

For the case where the dynamics can dominate, a sinker was added below the buoy where it will function something like a shock absorber and thereby reduce peak dynamic loads in the system. If this final size or mooring configuration is different from what was assumed in the above design analyses, another check iteration of the design procedure would be necessary. During installation this and all similar moorings are proof loaded, primarily to validate the anchors' holding capacities.

TABLE III. EXAMPLE HURRICANE MOORING DESIGN PROBLEM

<u>Item</u>	<u>Criteria</u>
Vessel	Two side-by-side minesweepers
Environmental Conditions	
Wind	99 mph (200 year, 30 second duration)
Current	3.5 fps ebb and flood
Storm Surge	3.8 feet
Water Depth	39 feet (35 foot water depth plus 3.8 storm surge)
Computed Loads	
Quasi-static	59 kips
Dynamic Peak	90 kips static plus peak dynamic
Design	
Mooring Class	C
Buoy	7 kips or more buoyancy
Chain	2 1/4" with cathodic protection
Sinker	13 kips each
Anchor	20 kip modified stockless (proof test holding power)

FLEETMOR PROGRAM
(called LOADMOOR during development)

The FLEETMOR program is a completely integrated, interactive user-friendly, quasi-static methodology which includes a number of graphic representations of results. Basically, it is a combination of LOAD and FLEET type program capabilities discussed earlier together with a number of additions. It is designed to compute the static response of the mooring system to wind, current, and wave drift forces. The effects of wave dynamics (heave, pitch, roll, sway, surge, and yaw) are not included. FLEETMOR can model from single- up to 24-point mooring systems where each leg may have up to three materials and a buoy and/or sinker. Line stretch is included to allow for the elongation of synthetic lines. Buoys are not confined to the water surface. Catenary equations are used to model the mooring legs.

FLEETMOR is menu-driven. To enter information, a series of screens are presented to the user asking for the appropriate problem information. The menus make it easy to modify input data in order to expedite parametric analyses. As the steady-state equilibrium configuration is being calculated, FLEETMOR internally computes new environmental loads for vessel heading changes, instead of the user having to compute the loads for different angles of incidence. The program can also find worst case conditions for a given range of environmental conditions. Final ship position and heading, mooring leg geometry, environmental loads, and line tensions can be presented in graphic and tabular form.

Of the three types of steady-state environmental loads (wind, current, and wave drift forces) wind loads are well understood and most accurately predicted. Recent studies of vessel wind loads have indicated the importance

of the ship's profile in estimating these loads (reference 6). FLEETMOR has eight vessel configuration categories to select from in determining the vessel's wind load characteristics: aircraft carriers, cruisers, destroyers, tankers, cargo ships, submarines, barges, and drydocks. This general approach to computing wind loads on ship-shaped vessels is similar to that in DM-26.5.

Current loads are not as well understood as wind loads. A recent survey of current-induced vessel load models showed poor agreement between the models and theories (reference 7). Much work is needed in this area before vessel current loads can be confidently predicted. Because of these limitations, FLEETMOR's current loads are approximate. FLEETMOR's current model includes form drag, friction drag, propeller drag, and shallow water effects (depth/draft < 3.0) for the vessel categories listed. The computation of current forces is discussed in reference 8 and is similar to the approach in DM-26.5.

The last environmental load computation is the second-order wave effect -- the steady wave drift force. This force is the least understood of the three environmental loads. It results from the vessel obstructing the transport of momentum in the wave field. The computation of the steady wave drift force is a simplified model, discussed in reference 8 in more detail.

While the methodologies used above are similar to those used in DM-26.5, the precise equations, coefficients, and techniques vary slightly, resulting in small differences in predicted behavior in some cases. FLEETMOR can directly model only two-dimensional mooring legs. The program offers the option of inputting load-deflection curves directly, as would be available from the EI program for example, so that more complex leg configurations can be handled.

SEADYN PROGRAM

SEADYN is a large general-purpose finite element program which analyzes large displacement cable dynamics. There are no limitations to the makeup of the moorings or cable structures. A single line may have many different materials, sinkers, buoys, or multiple lines attached to a single point. Either a catenary model or a finite element model may be used to simulate the cables. Line stretch is included in both models. Examples of problems that can be modeled include instrumentation arrays, vessel moorings, towing, and cable payout or pickup. SEADYN has been validated only for problems which involve cables and lumped bodies, and is currently being validated for vessel mooring problems.

The loading conditions which can be modeled are divided into three categories: steady winds, currents and concentrated loads with regular wave fields; with irregular wave fields; and time series excitations.

A static equilibrium configuration is calculated for steady loads; windgusting and current variations are ignored. Currents are divided into surface and subsurface currents. Surface currents and wind act only on vessels and surface buoys. Subsurface current profiles act on cables and all lumped bodies such as subsurface buoys and sinkers. Concentrated loads may be applied at any point in the model.

Either regular waves (a single sinusoid) or irregular waves (a sum of sinusoids) can be modeled to determine vessel and system dynamics. Only one wave train can be modeled at a time and is assumed to have a constant direction. SEADYN simulates wave effects for vessels only using a frequency domain analysis method. Heave, pitch, roll, sway, surge, and yaw motions are calculated. The effect of these vessel motions on the attached cables is then determined. Average, significant, and extreme values for tension and displacement are found for specified components. Slowly varying drift forces due to wave or wind are not included in the model at this time. SEADYN should not be used for problems with cresting or breaking waves.

A time domain analysis method can also be used to simulate dynamics. A displacement, velocity, or acceleration time series may be applied to some point of the model to determine the system's dynamic response.

Support programs are used to prepare input files for some types of problems. For problems involving wind and currents, LOADMOOR can be helpful in calculating vessel loads and in determining an initial mooring configuration. For vessel mooring dynamics, a data file with the vessel's response to waves must be created. A two-dimensional strip theory program or a three-dimensional diffraction theory program are used for this purpose.

Since SEADYN includes a general finite element cable model, it can be used to handle a variety of other ocean cable problems, e.g. lifting and lowering of objects, cable payout and pickup, and instrumentation arrays. The program is further described in reference 9.

EXAMPLE PROBLEM WITH FLEETMOR AND SEADYN

The general configuration and coordinate systems used in the example problems are shown in Figure 7. The current and wind are listed in Table IV where the headings are relative to the vessel bow. Eight different tests were simulated using FLEETMOR and SEADYN. The results are listed in Table IV.

TABLE IV. FLEETMOR AND SEADYN EXAMPLE PROBLEM

TEST NUMBER	CURRENT		WIND		FLEETMOR	SEADYN
	speed (kts)	heading (deg)*	speed (kts)	heading (deg)*		
1	1.33	-68	34	-83		
	bow (lb)				32700	24300
	stern (lb)				26900	26000
	ship position (ft)				89.5, 11.4	89.5, 10.4
	ship heading (deg)**				192	192
2	0.98	-104	20	-114		
	bow (lb)				12300	11700
	stern (lb)				9900	10500
	ship position (ft)				19.5, 1.4	19.5, 1.6
	ship heading (deg)				192	192
3	3.50	-70	23	-75		
	bow (lb)				92500	89800
	stern (lb)				70200	69200
	ship position (ft)				3.25, 1.1	3.15, 0.7
	ship heading (deg)				196	196
4	3.40	-74	24	-74		
	bow (lb)				86900	91300
	stern (lb)				71700	72000
	ship position (ft)				5.1, 4.2	8.9, 5.7
	ship heading (deg)				196	195
5	3.10	-49	20	-59		
	bow (lb)				47300	47400
	stern (lb)				26800	26800
	ship position (ft)				35.5, 17.4	38.5, 16.7
	ship heading (deg)				209	209
6	2.43	-61	21	-61		
	bow (lb)				25400	25500
	stern (lb)				15800	16900
	ship position (ft)				4.38, 2.4	0.8, 2.6
	ship heading (deg)				225	225

Notes: * Current and wind directions are relative to bow and in the local coordinate system shown in Figure 1
 ** Vessel position is relative to the initial guessed configuration and in the global coordinate system shown in Figure 2

The tensions calculated by FLEETMOR compare well for the same cases run by SEADYN. The calculated line tensions and ship position were virtually equal. Thus, given the same environmental loads, FLEETMOR and SEADYN will predict the same vessel position and mooring tensions.

Figure 8 is a picture of one of FLEETMOR's input screens. Figure 9 shows the program's graphical display of the output. Figures 10 and 11 show SEADYN's input and output files for the same problem. Obviously, FLEETMOR is much simpler to use; but it is more limited in the types of problems it can handle. SEADYN has been used to solve more difficult problems which FLEETMOR cannot handle.

CONTINUING DEVELOPMENT EFFORTS

SEADYN-86 is a very complex program and requires user entry of a finite element model of the mooring system. This version requires a minimum of several weeks to learn before meaningful simulations can be performed. Pre- and post-processors are being developed to make the program easier to use by simplifying data preparation and entry and providing support graphics. This package, called SEADYN-87 in Table I, will be undergoing evaluation during FY87.

The largest potential error in FLEETMOR and SEADYN (and most mooring programs) is the calculation of environmentally-induced loads on the vessel and mooring system. Recent full-scale mooring tests (reference 10) have shown that current and wave calculations are not well understood and need to be improved. The test data showed that a current gradient (non-uniform profile) may significantly alter the loads. The current drag loads measured differed by up to 50% from the loads predicted by the steady drag Morison equation. Investigation of this phenomenon is continuing.

Investigation is also continuing on how to improve the prediction of extreme events, such as hurricane waves, using a non-linear spectral analysis technique. The objective of this research is to provide a direct method for non-linear systems analysis based on stochastic data, particularly for application to dynamic structural analyses.

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FIGURE 1. TYPICAL SINGLE-POINT MOORING

FIGURE 2. TYPICAL MULTI-POINT MOORING SYSTEM FOR FLOATING DRY DOCK

FIGURE 3. LOAD VARIATION DUE TO VESSEL YAW

FIGURE 4. EXAMPLE COMPLEX MOORING LEG CONFIGURATION

FIGURE 5. MOORING LOAD-DEFLECTION CURVE

FIGURE 6. COMPUTED MOORING FORCE TIME HISTORY FOR SURGE

FIGURE 7. MOORING CONFIGURATION FOR FLEETMOR AND SEADYN EXAMPLE PROBLEM

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ENVIRONMENTAL INPUT SCREEN
=====
** VESSEL GROUPS ** DESCRIPTIVE INFORMATION ** PROBLEM NAME **
Name of vessel (up to 15 characters)
What is the number of mooring legs in this problem?
Site/purpose of mooring (up to 15 characters)
Initial heading of vessel (degrees)
CURRENT
What is the speed of the current in knots?
What compass angle is the current coming from?
What is the depth of the water?
WAVE
What is the significant wave height?
Do you know the wave period? (y/n)
What is the significant wave period?
What compass angle is wave direction coming from?
WIND
What is the wind velocity at 33 feet above the water line?
What compass angle is wind direction coming from?
Option: Revise (R), Delete (D), No Change (N), End (E) (save as shown).
  
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FIGURE 8. EXAMPLE FLEETMOR INPUT SCREEN

FIGURE 9. EXAMPLE FLEETMOR GRAPHIC OUTPUT

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1 LINE DIRECT LIST OF INPUT DATA FOR SEADYN
1 *T-2 TANKER IN CARQUINEZ STRAITS TEST #2610
2 *2 PT MOORING WITH ALL CATENARY CHAIN LEGS, WIRE HANSE, MOORING BOOT
3 * LOADMOOR WAS USED TO GET SHIP LOAD FILES
4
5 T-2 TANKER CARQUINEZ STRAITS TEST 2610 $$
6 PROB
7 16,12,-3,-1WS,1
8 FLOID
9 ,1
10 ,2
11 RATE
12 1,,25,65W9,30000000,1 * CHAIN
13 2,,25,5W9,10000000,1 * WIRE
14 NODE
15 1,-623,563,-80,3,3,3
16 2,712,490,-80,3,3,3
17 3,-386,191,0
18 4,422,159,0
19 13,,6,-3,0 * SHIP
20 14,W5,,85,W9,DEG
21 15,,265,1,20,-13,-13,-13
22 16,,277,-7,20,-13,-13,-13
23 LINE
24 0,1,3,,3,65,87000,1
25 0,2,4,,3,65,71700,1
26 4,3,15,2,,3,5,87000
27 4,4,16,2,3,5,71700
28 ELEM
29 1,1,3,,1,-1W10,-1
30 2,3,5,,2
31 6,11,15,,2,2
32 7,2,4,,1,-1W10,-2
33 8,4,6,,2
34 12,12,16,,2,2
35 TENS
36 1,1,1,1
37 2,6,1,3
38 7,7,1,2
39 8,12,1,4
40 LIMIT
41 1,-80,,1
42 2
43 LLOC
44 2,3,4,1
45 BODY
46 1,,30000,5
47 BLOC
48 1,3,4,1
49 FLOW
50 1,1,1,3,-1.3 * 1 KNOT FLOW AT -45 DEG TO BOW
51 SHIP
52 13,1M7,523,4040,17430,503,68,20,280000,50W23,80
53
54 MISSION CLASS T-2 TANKER... SLP VALUES TAKEN FROM LOADMOOR FOR VLCC
55 LBS FEET FT/SEC
56 1 523 4040 17430 503 68 20 280000
57 1 3 1 23.67 * WIND LOADS
58 0 90 180
59 900 6700 -180000
60 900 6700 -180000
61 900 6700 -180000
62 1 3 77 3.40 * CURRENT LOADS
63 0 90 180
64 9200 87100 -1370000
65 9200 87100 -1370000
66 9200 87100 -1370000
67 1
68 DEAD
69 FIX,3,131,132,133,141,142,143
70 SOLD
71 SAVE,-1
72 LIVE
73 SURF,3,4,-74.2
74 WIND,23.67,-74.2
75 FREE,131,132
76 SAVE,-1
77 LIVE
78 FREE,143
79 SURF,3,4,-74.2
80 WIND,23.67,-74.2
81 FIX,3,131,132
82 LIVE
83 FREE,131,132
84 SURF,3,4,-74.2
85 WIND,23.67,-74.2
86 END
  
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FIGURE 10. SEADYN-86 INPUT FOR EXAMPLE PROBLEM

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ISEADYN--T-2 TANKER CARQUINEZ STRAITS TEST 2610
STADY STATE INCREMENT = 1 LOAD FACTOR 0.10000E+01
MOOR FIXITY X Y Z ELT TENSION
1 3 3 3 -0.623000E+03 0.563000E+03 -0.800000E+02 1 0.612510E+05
2 3 3 3 0.712000E+03 0.490000E+03 -0.800000E+02 2 0.562446E+05
3 3 3 3 -0.384617E+03 0.195011E+03 0.000000E+00 3 0.562632E+05
4 3 3 3 0.423987E+03 0.159752E+03 0.000000E+00 4 0.562828E+05
5 3 3 3 -0.360194E+03 0.157311E+03 0.364146E+01 5 0.563029E+05
6 3 3 3 0.395064E+03 0.126587E+03 0.363332E+01 6 0.563335E+05
7 3 3 3 -0.335779E+03 0.119644E+03 0.746121E+01 7 0.581196E+05
8 3 3 3 0.366150E+03 0.934331E+02 0.745189E+01 8 0.531091E+05
9 3 3 3 -0.311372E+03 0.819696E+02 0.114591E+02 9 0.531276E+05
10 3 3 3 0.337247E+03 0.602918E+02 0.114495E+02 10 0.531471E+05
11 3 3 3 -0.286974E+03 0.443089E+02 0.116634E+02 11 0.531674E+05
12 3 3 3 0.308355E+03 0.271630E+02 0.156280E+02 12 0.512014E+05
13 3 3 3 0.843501E+01 0.256343E+00 0.000000E+00
14 3 3 0.000000E+00 0.000000E+00 0.632564E-02
15 S S S -0.252571E+01 0.656228E+01 0.200000E+02
16 S S S 0.279391E+03 -0.604960E+01 0.200000E+02
NUMBER OF ITERATIONS 10
CATENARY LENGTHS ON BOTTOM
ELT NO. LENGTH
1 0.694237E+02
7 0.798143E+02
  
```

FIGURE 11. SEADYN-86 OUTPUT FOR EXAMPLE PROBLEM